

Deep water

Character association and path coefficient analysis of deepwater rices

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Correlation and path coefficient analysis are important tools in determining the contribution of cultivar characters to yield and its components. Correlation coefficient reveals the association between two characters. Path analysis partitions correlation coefficients into direct and indirect effects and indicates the relative significance to yield for each component character.

Fifteen floating rices — local selections GT53, GT60, GT61, GT64, GT76, GT92, GT93, GT103, GT105, DW48, DW6172A, DW6255, GMS12, GMS13, and standard variety Jalmagna — were sown April 1979, before the onset of monsoons. Plots were 5 × 2 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Uncontrolled flooding started on 27 June, reached 280 cm 21 August, remained constant for about a week, and then gradually declined at 1-2

Table 2. Path coefficient analysis of deepwater rice characters

Character	Plant height	Panicle bearing tillers	Aquatic tillers/plant	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Correlation with yield
Plant height	0.76 ^a	0.16	0.06	0.23	-0.30	0.91
Panicle bearing tillers	-0.33	-0.36 ^a	0.02	-0.30	0.48	-0.49
Aquatic tillers/plant	-0.12	0.02	-0.35 ^a	0.51	-0.52	-0.34
Days to flowering	-0.07	-0.04	0.08	-2.33 ^a	2.50	0.14
Days to maturity	-0.09	-0.07	-0.07	-2.33	2.50 ^a	0.06
Residual			0.38			

^aDirect effect.

cm/ day.

The number of days to 50% flowering varied from 172 to 180; that to maturity was 196 to 215 days. Plant length varied from 290 cm for GT105 to 390 cm for Jalmagna.

Characters among the varieties studied differed significantly. Genotypic correlations were generally higher than phenotypic correlations. Only plant height showed a significant positive correlation with yield at both genotypic and phenotypic levels (Table 1). Other characters were not significantly associated with yield or with each other, except days to flowering and days to maturity.

Path analysis showed direct positive effects of plant height and days to maturity on yield (Table 2). Other

attributes had negative direct effects. But days to flowering showed maximum indirect effects, followed by panicle bearing tillers/ plant through days to flowering and number of aquatic tillers/ plant through days to flowering.

Plant height and days to maturity were the principal characters responsible for yield in these deepwater rices, but the positive residual indicates that other characters might also contribute.

Screening for ufra resistance in deepwater rice

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Ufra disease of rice, caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, causes serious deepwater rice crop losses in Bangladesh and several South Asian countries. Control methods exist but are not widely accepted. The following method of screening rice varieties for ufra was evolved in an experimental deepwater tank but could be adapted for field testing.

Layout and seedling establishment

1. Divide the tank into 1-m³ plots and make a 15- to 20-cm-high plastered mud levee around each plot. There should be 1 m between plots.
2. Sow rice seeds in line, with 15 cm between lines. Use one row for each variety. After germination thin to 20 seedlings/line.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients between 6 characters of deepwater rice, Uttar Pradesh, India.^a

Character ^b	Plant height	Panicle bearing tillers/plant	Aquatic tillers/plant	Days to flowering	Days to maturity
Yield/plot					
G	0.91**	-0.49	-0.34	0.14	0.04
Ph	0.51*	-0.27	-0.14	0.12	0.01
Plant height					
G		-0.44	-0.16	-0.10	-0.12
Ph		-0.30	-0.13	-0.10	-0.10
Panicle bearing tillers/plant					
G			-0.05	0.13	0.19
Ph			-0.08	0.07	0.12
Aquatic tillers/plant					
G				-0.22	-0.21
Ph				-0.17	-0.19
Days to flowering					
G					1.00**
Ph					0.94**

^a**P = 0.01, *P = 0.05. ^bG =genotypic, Ph = phenotypic.